

THE EFFECT OF OMEPRAZOLE ACE INHIBITORS, SITOTEK AND THEIR COMBINATIONS ON THE INDICATORS OF OXIDATIVE STRESS AND NO FORMATION IN THE GASTRIC MUCOSA

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Annotation. The study of the safety of the use of medicines is not only a clinical, but also an important socio-economic task, the solution of which can ensure the success of pharmacotherapy. The aim of the study was to identify and analyze drug adverse reactions (NPR) caused by drugs of the angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor group with the possibility of preventing their development and timely treatment. The most common among NPR are dry cough, bronchospasm, and allergic reactions. Other NSAIDs - hypotension, hyperkalemia, proteinuria, reversible acute renal failure - are less common. Special complications of drug therapy include angioedema and agranulocytosis. The method of spontaneous messages revealed an increase in blood pressure after taking enalapril.

Keywords: angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors; ACE inhibitors; adverse side reactions; NPR; pharmacotherapy.

The purpose of the study: to study the results of studying the effects of ACE, omeprazole and sitotek on the parameters of sex in the gastric mucosa

Materials and methods of research. Experimental studies were carried out on 78 male rats of a mixed population weighing 160-200 g, which were on a regular vivarium diet. The animals were divided into 13 groups of 6 individuals each.

Results of the study: Angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) plays an important role in the regulation of blood pressure and water-salt metabolism, but its effect on the stomach and digestive system also deserves attention. Regulation of blood supply: ACE is involved in the process of vasoconstriction, which can affect the blood supply to the stomach. This, in turn, can have an effect on gastric juice secretion and digestive processes. Effects on secretion: Studies show that ACE and its inhibitors can affect the secretion of gastrin, a hormone that stimulates the production of gastric juice. Changes in gastrin levels can lead to various digestive disorders. Pathological conditions: In some diseases, such as gastritis or peptic ulcer disease, there may be a change in ACE activity, which affects inflammatory processes and tissue healing. Effects on the microbiota: ACE can have an indirect effect on the intestinal microbiota, which is also important for the health of the stomach and the entire digestive tract. In general, ACE plays a multifaceted role in the functioning of the stomach and digestive system

Conclusions: Thus, the choice of a drug for the treatment of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs)-induced gastropathies in patients with rheumatological diseases presents significant difficulties, primarily due to the need for anti-ulcer treatment against the background of continued NSAID therapy. In many patients admitted to a rheumatology hospital due to an exacerbation of the underlying disease, when ulcers or erosions of the upper gastrointestinal tract are detected, NSAIDs cannot be canceled even temporarily, since this can lead to a significant deterioration and an increase in joint syndrome.

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